

A Theme of Decline and Disintegration of Family in William Faulkner's Novel *The Sound and The Fury*: A Critical Study

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Abstract:

The present study is a textual analysis of the novel, *The Sound and the Fury* by William Faulkner. It delves into the universal concepts of time, memory, and social changes. The study sought to analyze how the family disintegration takes place due to the inter-individual and intra individual differences. It also explores moral degradation of the Compson family. The characters in the novel represent lack of communication, material greed, emotional lacunas and Selfishness etc which lead to the downfall of Compson family. The study also focuses on the loss of moral values and its impact on the breakdown of kinship among the family members. The study also discusses loss of honor, purity and family integration. The material greed is the major cause for the degradation of the Compson family. The novel contains multiple levels of themes which are woven round the characters such as Benjy, Caddy, Jason and Dilsey. Though the family is social institution, the ethical values of the family structure depend on the individual integrity. To cherish the dignity, tradition of the family, every family member of the Compson family has neglected the norms, taboos, customs of the Southern American culture and we find the downfall of the Compson family.

Keywords: Family, Compson, Southern, Disintegration etc.

Introduction:

William Faulkner is popular Southern-American novelist who has depicted the decaying social, aristocratic and moral culture of the Southern American society in his literary work. His novel *The Sound and The Fury* delves into disintegration of Compson family which represents the fragmented cultural, moral values of the South America. Faulkner has borrowed this title from Shakespeare's play *Macbeth*. The title itself implies the perplexing state of the mind, confusion and meaninglessness and fragmented condition of the Compson family. A novel substantiates the loss of earlier Southern-American family institution due to incompetency of the family members to establish trustworthy family relations. The Compson family is not able

to adapt with new upcoming social challenges and they only stick to the outdated customs and falls notions of family prestige. He gives broader perspectives of the fragmentation of Compson family. In any social structure family is that kind of institution where the charity of all the individual begins but during the 20th century Southern American families underwent drastic changes because of social dynamics occurred in the South America. The characters of Benjy and Caddy stand symbolic. They represent their innocent nature, sentimental world and the ethical integrity of the Compson family. The characters of Jason, Quentin and Caddy, Benjy stand quite emblematic which reflects the loss of earlier South American family culture. The novel discusses the rigidity of social ethics, domination of patriarchy, material

possessiveness, and lack of emotional and affectionate trustworthy relationship lead to moral degradation and social aloofness. Faulkner depicts the Compson family as a cross section of a disintegration of South American family. The major aspects of this novel are decline of the orthodox southern royal-aristocratic family due to the domestic issues of the family members of the Compson family. Once the Compson family had the dignity, respect and social prestige but social status and reputation of that family had under the estimated. Due to the lack of family ethics, tendency of selfishness and sense of inability has led to the disintegration of their family. Time plays very significant role in the novel. The character of Benjy didn't distinguish the present span of his life from the earlier life span that is past. The character of Quentin is haunted with the past. The character from the Compson family is materially haunted and only concentrates on the present situation of the family by focusing on material gain. William Faulkner discusses the issue of the universal time and its perception on the members of the Compson family.

The writer has experimented with stream of consciousness technique by applying fragmented time structure and has depicted tragic disintegration of the Compson family. As we put this novel literary research framework, it deals with multiple dilemmas on the psychological, social and ethical level which paves way to the decline of orthodox Southern American culture. It focuses on the Southern American decaying family culture. It points out the transformation of Southern American Society post-civil war. The research scholars have poignantly brought out the perspectives of the isolation and alienation by depicting the typical characters such as Benjy, Quentin and Jason. Benjy represents communication barrier. Quentin represents whimsical and perturbed state of mind. Jason

represents bitterness and selfishness of human being. The writer has effectively portrayed the character of Dilsey who represent true and dedicated love, loyalty and his nature of sacrifice. Till to the end Dilsey exhibits the moral qualities. The novel contains metaphorical aspects of the decaying culture of American Old South.

Family As Social Institution and It's Reciprocity with Literature in the Context of the Selected Text:

No literature come into existence without society. German thinker **Karl Marx has aptly stated that Literature is an expression of the society**. Family is the major institution of the society. Society determines the norms, taboos, custom and tradition of any family. As part of the society and family, writer witnesses all the worldly wiseness. It establishes the reciprocal relationship and depicts whatever he has witnessed and seen in his contemporary society. The kinship in the family depends on the ethical dimensions of the family structure. The charity begins at home. It means the family may be in joint or nuclear but the psychological and societal dimensions play crucial role to conserve the oldest values and ethics of the family. Most of the literary texts are confined with family dilemmas which becomes an integral part to understand the human nature and perplexed psychological state.

The present novel is an outcome of the South American decaying family structure due to the loss of ethical and values of kinship amongst the members of the Compson family. As the writer of frontier movement in Southern America, he has closely seen dilapidated old Southern American valuable family structure due to intra individual differences across the Southern American states. The Compson family represent universal truth through its morbid behaviour of the family. The text selected here discusses the lack of interest the members of the Compson

family to conserve the family tradition. The study sought to analyze the text in the frame of societal regress and disintegration of the Southern American family. The Compson family represents the decaying structure of the family. The study put the efforts to find out Faulkner's depiction of the declining family structure of the American Southern Aristocracy. Literature and perception of the social institutions such as marriage and family are always depicted by the writer since it's existence. Even the epics also contains family perspectives across the world literature. So, Faulkner's *The Sound and The Fury* is a foundational text which societal document which is considered as magnus opus in the history of Southern American Literature. Each section of the novel establishes the realistic condition of the Southern American society.

Selected Text in the Psychological Perspectives:

The characters in this novel dominate the plot of the novel. There are different kinds of personality types whose behaviour affects adversely on the Compson family structure. The disintegration in the novel is not due to the social dynamism but it occurs only by the abnormal psychological states of the characters. Benjy dots on the past, he can't survive with present. He is lingering in the past and enjoys the earlier life by the old memories. Quentin is obsessed with lost tradition and tradition. He suffers from maladjustment with family members. It represents the family structure of the Compson dominated by patriarchal tradition. There is another contrary character Jason who represent Epicurean way of life who is obsessed with material world. The novel deals with psychological The Fall and The Decline of Compson family. Due to the inter and intra individual difference the family has got victimised of disintegration. We find prodigious traits of human nature in this novel. The major

issue of the novel deals with inferiority and various psychological complexes. The character of Caddy stands special attention to the readers through its complexity of nature. All the characters become the aspects of the personality types as discussed by Jungian theory. They are introverts, extroverts as well as ambivert by nature.

Theoretical Discussion on the Selected Text- *The Sound and The Fury:*

William Faulkner's novel *The Sound and The Fury* is seminal book on the decaying family culture of Southern American states. As the writer of the frontiers, he discusses the major domestic issues related to the Compson family. This family is considered as the home of charity and it has full of social respect. Due to the dynamic nature of social changes this family has gone under drastic changes and the family members have accepted the new changes occurred in upcoming world. Each character stands symbolic in the novel. The character of Quentin is interested in the past life and he neglects whatever he has the responsibilities in his family. He goes away from the sacred duties of his family, instead he gets involved in the past events. Caddy stands symbolic character in this novel. She rebels against restricted social norms. She stands central sentimental figure in the novel. She doesn't narrate any section of the novel. Her loss of innocence is major cause for the downfall of Compson family.

The novel explores the loss of the moral values. It deals with decay of honour, purity and family integration. The character of Quentin rejects dynamic nature and moral standards of the society. Jason is the symbol of greed and cruelty. The declining moral reflects the larger orthodox change in the Southern State of America. Every characterisation depicted in novel is symbol of isolation and alienation. Benjy is lacking in communication, Quentin is mentally disturbed

and Jason is isolated due to his selfish nature. The inheritance of all these demerits we find the sudden breakdown of the Compson family. The character of Dilsey stands contrasting to the other characters because he inherits patient, strength and ethical upright. Benjy is mentally disabled and he is youngest son of the Compson family. He has communicative barrier and only he is emotionally attached to the memories of his sister Caddy. He is symbol of innocence and purity.

The character of Quentin Compson is psychologically complex character. He is obsessed with family respect. He never reconciles with reality. His idealism leads to emotional turmoil. He delays and that cause the lack of coordination. His family gets in dilemmas. Jason Compson is the symbol of materialism and moral corruption. The character of Jason stands as moral degradation of the Compson family. Caddy Compson is sentimental character which loses innocence and that is the main cause for the downfall of the Compson family. Dilsey is the loyal servant who represent love, kindness and ethical stability. She has very strong sentiments. She symbolises ethical strength.

Findings:

The novel discusses the contemporary issue of disintegrated Compson family. The characters represent the realistic decaying culture of Southern American Society. The plot of the novel discusses the physicals as well as mental clashes amongst the individuals represented in the

novel. The novel is contemporary reflection on the Southern American decaying Compson family.

Conclusions:

The study explores the time, memory, morality and social transformation. It focuses the issue of the family disintegration by the modernist approach of the members of the Compson family. It also focuses on the psychological traits of the characters represented in the novel. William Faulkner as the writer of Southern American state, he has manipulated the decaying culture of the Compson family very effectively in his seminal novel *The Sound and the Fury*.

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